

STUDENTS' ATTITUDE, A DETERMINANT OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN HISTORY

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Abstract

The study was conducted to find out how attitude of students determine their academic achievement in senior secondary schools in history. The qualitative analysis was adopted to carry out the study. The study established that attitude of students affect their academic achievement. From the findings it was concluded that parents should be aware of the needs to create an enabling home environment that is conducive for the education of their children. In view of importance of History, the study made the following recommendations: that the subject should be given adequate attention in terms of policy statement; qualified teachers with positive attitude towards the subject should be employed and encouraged: teachers should be allowed to attend seminars and workshops on Psycho-Social variables that can affect the academic abilities of the student; practical approach or method of teaching should be used often to make the teaching of the subject more interesting and meaningful .and also students should be encouraged to develop positive attitude towards History as a subject.

Keywords:- Students, Attitude, Academic Achievement and Secondary Schools

Introduction

Academic achievement can be explained as the learning outcome of students in their academic studies in the school. In evaluating this, the

cognitive: domain of students is assessed to determine their performance. Academic achievement in any subject is dictated by certain variables which, among others, could be psychological or sociological, such variables constitute a complex network of forces that influence the academic achievement of an individual or group of learners, (Elugbemi, 2001).

In the work of Elugbemi (2001), Bloom and his colleagues of the Chicago School, identified three educational environments - the home, school and the peer group - as being the variables that exert influence on the Educational achievement of students in schools. Osokoya (1996) indicated that the attitude of students in the school curriculum has a bearing on achievement; hence the development of positive attitudes towards school subjects had long been a major goal of educators. In essence, the concern of students' attitudes towards traditional subjects in school curriculum has declined with regard to the possibility of decreasing enrolment. Students' enrolment in Secondary School Certificate Examination in History had been declining in the recent past and educators had been calling for the improvement of students' attitudes to the subject, (Osokoya, 1996 and 2001).

Meanwhile, the new National Policy on Education in Nigeria which came into effect in 1977 and revised thrice thereafter (1981, 1998 and 2004) removed History teaching from the curriculum of Junior Secondary Schools and replaced it with Social Studies (Osokoya, 1996) This, course, led to unpopularity of the subject at the Senior Secondary School level, ((Osokoya, 2001). In a national survey among student offering Arts subjects at the secondary school level, Osokoya (1996 and 2001) established that students run away from the subject because its contents are too voluminous and thus difficult to pass. The resultant effect of its unpopularity is that, many of the Nigerian secondary school students preferred other Social Subjects such as Government, Economics and Geography to study of History.

Scholars in the field of educational psychology and sociology hold the view that psycho-social factors exert a domineering influence on all the facets of life of an individual. Thus, Onocha (1985) and Osokoya (2006), for example, claimed that man is guided and ruled by the psychological and social variables in his environment. Psycho-social variables such as study habits, test anxiety, locus of control, interest in schooling, self concept, perception, attitude, motivation, aggressiveness, seriousness of purpose and socio-economic status of parents, play an important role not only in the academic achievement of pupils but, also in their affective learning outcome, studied like those of Odinko and Adeyemo (1999), Onocha, (1985), and Osokoya (1996), have supported the fact that psycho-social variables come into play in predicting academic performance, while other studies like that of Fawole, (2006) observed that raw materials of the teaching profession and living human beings, in essence, teachers concentrate on what and how to teach that they often neglect who to teach. It is equally important to note that it is professionally necessary for teachers to be well equipped in their teaching techniques and subject matter. Teachers must also be well knowledgeable in the psychological and sociological make up of their students.

A number of scholars agreed that when students have positive self concept, they are likely to develop positive attitude toward school subject while the reverse will be the case for those who have negative self concept. Osokoya (1996) and (2001) observed in his studies that how a student feels (self concept) as far as History learning is concerned could significantly predict his attitude towards the subject. Elugbemi (2001) investigated college students' attribution for general academic performance and their achievement in specific courses. They reported that internal locus of control is a characteristic of high achievers. Elugbemi (2001) further reported that personal control or acceptance of personal responsibility for learning is found to be associated with higher academic performance among Philippine

students. In a study of Australian College students, Elugbemi (2001) found that there was little relationship between locus of control and first year academic success. This finding is in line with the view that internal locus of control is related to outcome, (Elugbemi, 2001).

However, Literature reviewed that the previous work had not attained a reasonable degree of success in identifying the order and strength of the interaction between the identified psychological and social variables and effective learning outcome in History. It is on this note that this present study investigates the effect of students' attitude as determinant of academic achievement of senior secondary schools History in Kwara State.

Relevance of History

The inclusion of and emphasis on History in the Nigerian secondary school curriculum are born out of its usefulness to the learners on one hand and the society on the other hand. History, more than any other subject in the secondary school curriculum, quickens the understanding of national heritage as it provides information on what the society is, how it grows, the way it works, its problem and achievement. Adequate knowledge of the evolution and development of the society provides clues to factors operating in them; the current and force as well as the motives and conflicts both general and personal that move and shape her events. Most of the national difficulties today stem from its history either ultimate or proximate, (Osokoya, 1996). cursory acquaintance with the history of Nigerian state, show that the socio-economic and political difficulties are traceable in the main ethnic chauvinism which is a carry over from the shoddy integration of diverse people by a colonial power without regard to their sensibilities into a nation.

The subject matter History, if properly understood, engenders in students a more tolerant out look as well as an enlargement of human. This is

a major prerequisite for building a virile nation among heterogeneous groups such as Nigeria. Furthermore, as the ancient Roman orator Cicero earlier remarked "for a people to be ignorant of its history is for a man to be without memory and thus making the same discoveries that have been made in the past, invent the same technique, wrestle with the same problems, committing the same errors and forfeiting the rich pleasures of recollection (Osokoya, 1996).

However, in spite of individual and co-operate gains derived from the teaching and learning of this traditional subject at the secondary school level, it has become increasingly unpopular among the Nigerian students. The new National Policy on Education which came into effect in 1977 and revised thrice thereafter (1981, 1998 and 2004) removed history teaching from curriculum of Junior Secondary schools and replaced it with Social Studies. This, of course, led to the unpopularity of the subject at the Senior Secondary School level (Osokoya, 1996 and Osokoya, 2001). In a national survey among students offering arts subjects at Senior Secondary School level Osokoya, (1996 and 2001) established that students run away from the subject because its content is too voluminous and thus difficult to pass. The resultant effect of its unpopularity is that many of the Nigerian secondary school students preferred other Social Science subjects such as Government, Economics and Geography to the study of History. Table 1 shows the analysis of students who enrolled and took History, Government, Economic and Geography at the West African Examination Council (WAEC), Senior Secondary School Certificate between 1990 and 2004.

Table 1 analysis of Nigerian student's enrolment for History, Government, Economics and Geography in the WAEC School Certificate Examination 1990 2004.

Year	Total Entry WAEC	Total Entry for History	% of History Students	Total Entry for Govt.	% of Govt. Students	Total Entry for Economics	% of Economics Students	Total Entry for Geography	% of Geography Students
1990	339,718	17,094	5.03	85,622	25.20	174,808	51.46	23,354	6.87
1991	299,323	54,011	18.04	115,412	38.56	240,224	80.26	169,908	56.76
1992	405,526	22,562	5.56	151,366	37.33	313,072	77.20	214,709	52.94
1993	443,841	28,116	6.33	267,598	75.36	355,083	80.00	293,642	66.15
1994	480,513	62,996	13.11	267,598	57.31	466,971	97.18	310,227	64.56
1995	434,315	34,757	8.00	253,694	63.69	398,322	91.71	297,322	68.45
1996	516,196	67,207	13.02	288,347	55.86	484,508	93.86	319,118	61.82
1997	622,433	72,823	11.69	355,489	57.11	582,926	93.65	382,663	61.47
1998	640,626	65,386	10.21	392,280	61.23	651,426	98.34	428,761	66.92
1999	761,088	70,597	8.28	426,274	56.00	717,309	94.27	463,400	60.88
2000	877,549	47,709	5.44	513,622	58.52	804,458	91.67	382,433	43.57
2001	452,608	30,784	6.80	263,079	58.12	417,863	92.32	212,724	49.98
2002	925,289	66,841	7.22	552,289	59.69	868,532	93.87	531,599	57.45
2003	1,004,319	42,274	4.21	606,718	60.41	915,923	91.20	377,990	37.63
2004	643,378	42,036	6.53	345,617	53.72	607,630	94.44	372,665	57.92

Source: WAECR Research and statistics Unit, Osokoya, (2006) and Saliu (2014)

From table 1, it was only in 1991, 1994, 1996, 1997 and 1998 that over 10% of the total entry, WAEC registered for History as a subject at the School Certificate Examination. The proportion of students offering History at senior

secondary school level was as low as 4.2% in the year 2003. The same table show that 60.4% and 91.20% of candidates for WAEC/SSCE in 2003 enrolled for Government and Economics respectively. The enrolment of students for Government ranged between 25.20% in 1990 and 75.36% in 1993. Similarly, Economics had a minimum enrolment of 51.46% in 1990 and as high as 98.34% in 1998. It is interesting to observe that Geography which is another traditional subject in the Nigerian Secondary School Curriculum was highly patronized by students over the years as shown in the table 1. In 11 out of the 15 years period analyzed, more than 50% of all students that enrolled for WAEC/SSCE sat for Geography. In 1995 the percentage of students who took Geography in WAEG/SSCE rose to 68.45%. Similarly over 60% of students that enrolled for WAEC/SSCE sat and took Geography in the year 1993, 1994, 1995, 1996, 1997, 1998, 1999.

Apart from the record of low enrolment of students offering History at the School certificate level, the performance of such students in the subject over the year has been a matter of concern to educators. Table 2 shows the analysis of students' performance at the Senior Secondary School Certificate Examination in History conducted by WAEC during the period.

Source: WAEC Research and Statistics Unit (Osokoya, 2006) and Saliu (2014)

Year	Percentage of students who enrolled and took History
1990	25.20%
1991	37.90%
1992	37.90%
1993	75.36%
1994	60.4%
1995	68.45%
1996	60.4%
1997	60.4%
1998	60.4%
1999	60.4%
2000	60.4%
2001	60.4%
2002	60.4%
2003	4.2%

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Year	No that Sat for Exam	Credit 1 – 6	Passes 7 & 8	F9	% in Grades 1-6	% in Grade F9
1990	14,566	6,404	3,357	4,805	43.96	28.11
1991	51,330	16,922	9,492	24,916	32.97	46.13
1992	13,604	4,677	2,803	6,124	34.38	27.14
1993	18,145	10,384	2,777	4,984	57.23	17.73
1994	58,790	19,180	10,323	29,287	32.62	45.76
1995	23,372	10,753	4,505	8,114	46.01	23.34
1996	60,837	16,358	9,729	34,750	26.89	51.71
1997	66,214	13,979	11,497	40,738	21.11	55.94
1998	56,288	12,052	9,881	34,355	21.41	52.54
1999	60,348	14,983	11,657	33,708	24.83	47.75
2000	25,092	8,231	5,453	11,408	32.80	23.91
2001	18,614	4,244	3,551	10,819	22.80	35.14
2002	54,365	15,091	13,651	25,623	27.76	38.33
2003	41,577	26,162	5,205	10,210	62.92	24.15
2004	35,379	8,472	6,384	20,523	23.95	48.82

Sources: WAEC Research and Statistics Unit and Osokoya, (2006).

A critical examination of table 2 reveals that 62.92% was the highest performance for students with credit (1-6) grade in the year 2003. This was followed by 57.23% in 1993. On the other hand, 55.94% of the students who took History were recorded to have failed in the year 1997. This was closely followed by 51.71% failure in the subject in the year 1996.

Theoretical Framework

The target of the study is premised on attitude of students therefore theories that have to do with the characteristics of this variable as it affects learning will be applicable This study will be guided by the following theory Baumrind's Theory of parenting styles.

In order to understand parents' influence on their children and parent-child relationship, theorists have attempted to conceptualize and operationalise parenting styles into meaningful categories, notable among these theories is Baumrind's theory of parenting styles (Baumrind, 1996). The latter stands apart from others because it conceptualized parenting as varying in terms of a single domain of control. Baumrind divided parenting control into three types, that is authoritative parents, authoritarian parents and permissive parents. The beauty of this theory is in the exploration of the dynamics of how parents and children influence one another not only at the infancy but well into adolescence.

The parenting style most frequently and solidly associated with healthy, well-adjusted children in the existing literature is authoritative parenting which has become the benchmark for comparing and assessing different styles. Authoritative parenting combines high levels of warmth with moderate level of control. It is often contrasted with permissive parenting (high or low warmth, combined with low levels of control) and authoritarian parenting (high levels of control). Authoritative parenting reflects a combination of two scales: warmth and responsiveness on one scale and control and demanding on the other (Saliu, 2014). When parents are very emotionally warm, available and affectionate and balance these qualities with consistently high expectations and firm but fair disciplinary style, they create an emotional climate in which children thrive.

Accordingly, children from authoritative homes achieve high performance in schools. (Saliu 2014), Review of authoritative parenting studies, reported that adolescents from homes where authoritative parenting is the norm achieve more in school, report less depression and anxiety and tend to score higher on measures of self-reliance and self-esteem (Baumrind, 1996 and Saliu, 2014). He highlighted three ways that authoritative parenting yields healthier children and adolescents.

1. Nurturing and parent involvement make children more receptive to their parents' influence;
2. The children combination of support and structure help children develop self-regulatory skills and competence;
3. Verbal give and take between parents and children fosters cognitive and social skills.

Although Baumrind's (1996), theory has been influential, for only a limited number of facilities. (Darling and Steinberg, 1993). That is, Baumrind's typology did not account for parents who do not clearly fit into a single category, not did it account for parents who do not belong in any of the categories.

Students' Attitude and Academic Achievement

At the centre of all academic activities, is the student. The goal of every school activity is to cultivate knowledge in the student. However this goal can only be achieved when certain students' factors are taken into consideration, students' factors like test anxiety, attitude to the subject, parental influence and peer group, (Fawole, 2006).

Attitude towards a subject could be said to have a direct link with achievement in that subject, because a person would generally perform better in any task to which he is favourably disposed. Osoakoya (1996),

Osokoya (2001) and Saliu (2014) also claimed that attitude towards a subject is the basis of cognitive development and motivation. Osokoya (1996) and Saliu (2014) also reported in their studies that interest in schooling could predict students' attitude to a subject, particularly History. They also stated that the study is in agreement with Odinko and Adeyemo (1999) when they discovered that interest in schooling was the most potent predictor of students' attitude towards English Language.

Pressures have strong effect on learning outcomes of students in secondary schools. Anxiety is an unpleasant, complex and varying patterns of behaviour which people show when reacting to the internal (that is thoughts and feelings) or external (environmental situations) stimuli. Anxiety in its various forms of manifestations can have debilitating effects and incapacitate both psychologically and cognitively, (Fawole, 2006 and Osokoya, 1996).

Fawole (2006) reported that worry, tension, test relevant thoughts, physical reactions (rapid heart beat) and fear of failure are among the traits found in a test anxious person. Theoretically, anxiety is said to induce a generalized attention deficit, (Saliu, 2014). For instance, if a child becomes a victim of overdose of anxiety before entering examination hall, the child will experience performance decrement at the examination leading to possible examination failure, (Fawole, 2006). Fawole (2006) further argued that the test anxiety affects academic performance because test anxious students develop feeling of inadequacy, loss of status, self-esteem and helplessness. Thus, high level of anxiety is detrimental to academic achievement. However, some dosage of anxiety is necessary for healthy personality because it helps reaction against danger and has adaptive effects, which helps to promote one into action in tackling some of the of daily

living of which learning is one (Osokoya, 1996 and Saliu 2014). Another variable closely related to the foregoing is the attitude of students towards the subject as it affects the learning outcome. The negative (interest) attitude of students to some subjects has been responsible for the low enrolment of students in such subjects, (Osokoya, 1996). Most student often claim that certain subjects like History is too voluminous and also difficult to pass at the senior secondary level. (Osokoya, 2001), Interest of a student towards a subject is a major determinant in his achievement in it.

Fawole, (2006) opined that it is a student that develops a negative attitude towards examinations, this negative attitude may seriously interfere with his or her performance in the examination. They stressed that attitude works hand in hand with learner's will power. A candidate who has a negative attitude towards a subject, may find his attitudinal frame of mind negating his performance in such subject's examination.

Poor study habits invariably affect academic performance through a system of behaviors' which are non-consistent with efficient learning at the acquisition, retention or reproduction stages of that process. Behaviors such as inadequate or poor time allocation, delay or non-completion of homework assignments, defective note-taking, poor concentration, lack of teacher consultation and defective examination strategies distort or limit the material acquired and stored during the learning process and reproduction of the learned material during examination, (Osokoya, 1996). This is contrary to the submissions of Odinko and Adeyemo (1999) with respect to study habit.

Fawole, (2006) and Saliu, 2014 studied the relationship between learning History and students' attitude. They discovered that learning History is closely associated with student' attitude towards the subject. Attitude towards a subject greatly affects achievement.

Peer group is another variable that exerts great influence on students personality and preference. Onasanya, (1991), Adu and Saliu (2014) asserted that peer groups have the power to bring about the success or failure of their group members. This is because the groups often have the power to punish by open shame (ridicule) and reward by applause. The peer group therefore exercise some influence on individual personalities and their will power.

Osonwa, Adejobi and Iyam (2013) observed that the falling academics standard and the influencing factors include the economic status of the parents.

Owing to the present economic situation in the country, many poor parents are forced by circumstance to saddle the young ones with chores like hawking wares, cleaning the house and doing other menial jobs around the house before going to school and after school hours. Domestic chores like these, no doubt, help train the children and make them realize that they can and should contribute their own quota to the general up keep of the family. However, when parents and guardians burden their children with work excessively, leaving little or no study time for the children, their school work is bound to suffer (Osonwa, Adejobi, Iyam 2013 and Saliu, 2014).

Saliu (2014) further Lamented that street hawking among young school students have psychological imposed other problems like sex networking behaviour, juvenile-delinquent behaviour, which take much of the student school time that necessitated the poor academic performance and drop out syndrome noticed among young school students. nevertheless, they also lamented that the maternal and paternal deprivation of the essential needs of the young students have prompted their poor performance in public examination such as Junior secondary School certificate (JSSC), West African School certificate

Examination (WASCE).

Conclusion

The findings of early research works carried out by researchers like Odinko and Adeyemo (1999), Osokoya (2001) and Osokoya (1996) established that psycho-social variables come into play in predicting academic performance of students in school subjects. Therefore parent should be aware of the needs to create an enabling home environment that is conducive for the education of their children. A hostile home environment will inhibit the attitude adjustment of the children and may eventually have adverse effect on their learning and academic achievement in History. Teachers as well should adopt good teaching methods to motivate students of History.

Recommendations

This study is therefore recommends that:

The subject should be given adequate attention in term of policy towards statement.

Students should be encouraged to develop positive attitude towards History as a subject. Teachers should be allowed to attend seminars and workshops on Psycho-Social variables that can affect the academic abilities of the students.

Parents should be sensitized to the important roles that the home environment plays in the academic achievement of their children.

Parents should always strive to provide their children with History textbooks.

Practical approach or method of teaching should be used often to make the teaching of the subject more interesting and meaningful.

In order to achieve high academic achievement he home and the

school should always see each partners in progress for education of students.

REFERENCES

- Baumind, D. (1991) The influence of Parenting styles on adolescent competency and substance use. *Journal of Early Adolescent*
- Baumrind .D. (1996) Effects of authoritative control of child behaviour child development.
- Elugbemi, S. A. (2001) A causal model, of some psycho-social variables as determinants of primary school pupils Academic achievement in social studies, unpublished, M.Ed. Thesis University of Ibadan.
- Fawole, A. Y. (2006) Social and Students factors as Determinant of achievement in history at the Secondary School level in Oyo State. Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis University of Ibadan.
- Odinko, M. N; AdeyemO, D. A. (1999) Students Socio-psychological Achievement, in Senior Secondary English Language. *African Journal of Educational Research* 5(1) 126 131.
- Osokoya, I. D. (1996) *Writing and Teaching of History: A guide to Advance Study* Ibadan: Leonard Educational Publishers Ltd.
- Osokoya, I. O. (2001) A Causal Model 'of some Psycho-social factors as Determinants of Senior Secondary Students attitude towards history.
- Osokoya, I .O. (2006) *History and Policy of Education in the world Perspective* Ibadan: Leonard Educational Publishers Ltd.
- Saliu, K.A. (2014) Some Psycho-socio factors as determinants of academic achievement of Senior Secondary School History in Kwara State Unpublished M. Ed. Thesis University of Ibadan.